

Role of Britain in South Asia during Early Years of Cold War

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This paper analyzes the role of Britain in India-Pakistan relationship from 1947 to 1971. During the initial years after the independence of India and Pakistan, Britain very clearly tilted towards Pakistan. Britain was part of NATO and its tilt towards Pakistan was completely logical from cold war's point of view. There was so much anger in India against Britain that a bill was tabled in parliament that demanded Indian withdrawal from Commonwealth. On thorny issue of Kashmir, Britain supported Pakistan's position and scathingly criticized India. Pakistan became the member of CEATO in 1954 and of CENTO in 1955. Britain itself was party to these treaties. Thus, Britain got more reasons to support Pakistan against India, which had adopted a policy of non-alignment under the leadership of Prime Minister Nehru. In comparison to India's non-alignment policy, Pakistan openly attached itself to Britain and America. During 1965 war between India and Pakistan, British Prime Minister Wilson accused India of aggression. During the 1971 war of India and Pakistan, Britain again tilted towards Pakistan. This paper uses historical and comparative methodology to understand the policy of Britain towards India and Pakistan from 1947 to 1971.

Kashmir War of 1948 and British Policy

India was partitioned in 1947 on religious lines and a new country Pakistan, having Muslim majority, came into existence. Princely state of Kashmir was uniquely situated between India and Pakistan. Kashmir had Muslim majority but was ruled by a Hindu king. On October 22, 1947, Pakistani Pashtun tribal crossed the border of the Kashmir in order to capture of the state. Kashmiri king signed the instrument of accession with India on October 26, 1947. Indian troops were airlifted to Srinagar, capital of state, and stopped the onward movement of tribal militia. Pakistani forces entered into picture in late 1948. A formal ceasefire line was established on January 1, 1949. By the time, hostilities ended, Pakistan had captured one-third part of Kashmir, while India retained Kashmir valley, Jammu and Ladakh. Britain played an important role in the war between nascent countries. Since Britain had just left the subcontinent, it still enjoyed deep influence in South Asia. In fact, due to botched up process of partition, Britain was directly responsible for Kashmir conundrum. Britain markedly tilted towards Pakistan. Nehru took the Kashmir issue to the United Nations and there it became a pawn of cold war politics.

Britain unhesitatingly and rather irresponsibly brought religious angle also in the problems. British Foreign Office reminded Muslim countries that:

HMG might easily have handed over entire India to Hindu majority. But they loyally protected the Muslim minority, even to the point of facilitating a separate Muslim state by going out of their way. This is what the Muslim themselves demanded. We have recognized Pakistan as a dominion and supported its admission to UNO. We would always come to Pakistan's help.

It is hardly surprising that a high-ranking British official remarked that official eyes have been closed to make facilities available to tribesmen. There was largely held view in London that it was morally and practically binding on UK that the maximum pressure should be exerted on India to bring them out of the narrow legalism of their case.¹ Archibald Nye, British High Commissioner to India, succinctly summed up British bias against India:

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¹ ANKIT, RAKESH. "1948: The Crucial Year in the History of Jammu and Kashmir." *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 45, no. 11, 2010, pp. 49–58. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/25664224

No doubt that India has sinned more than Pakistan. Nehru is very emotional-not disposed to see reason. The problem is a psychological one. What tactics to adopt with this particular man in this special circumstance to achieve our objectives. Put aside the merits of the case—its legalities and technicalities. This is no time to think of right or wrong and the details of the case must be risen over to give the broad view.²

Thus British shenanigans were becoming clear from 1948 onwards. It favored Pakistan because it assumed that in longer term Pakistan would be a better friend and it cannot be allowed to collapse because it would bring chaos in North West Frontier Province. British also feared the USSR might intervene in the conflict on behalf of Pakistan and a threatened Pakistan might even welcome it.³

Pakistan's Entry into SEATO and CENTO and British Policy

Pakistan became a member of South East Asian Treaty Organization (SEATO) or Manila pact in 1954 and Central Treaty Organization or Baghdad pact in 1955. These military pacts were sponsored by the US and Britain. CENTO or Middle East Treaty Organization was formed by Iran, Iraq, Turkey, Pakistan and Britain. US joined in 1958. SEATO was formed by Australia, France, New Zealand, Pakistan, Philippines, Thailand, Britain and the US. These were typical cold war military pacts, which were motivated by keeping the USSR out from Middle East and South East Asia. Pakistan, by becoming the members of these pacts, brought cold war calculus officially in South Asia. In preparation for bringing Pakistan into these organizations, the US, with the full knowledge of Britain, approved military assistance to Pakistan on February 7, 1954. to Pakistan. However British government did not take Indian objections into consideration and enthusiastically supported the idea of military aid to Pakistan. Indeed, it was in line with general policy and attitude of British government towards collective security systems against communist expansion in South and South East Asia.⁴

On October 20, 1962, China launched two simultaneous attacks on India—one in Ladakh and other across the McMahon Line. Chinese troops advanced in both theaters, overcoming Indian resistance. China declared a ceasefire on November 20, 1962 and declared that it had taught a punitive lesson to India. The war was an out and out humiliation for India. During the same time the US was involved in Cuban Missile Crisis with the USSR and thus Washington allowed London to take a leading role in India-China war. Whatever good Anglo-American front achieved by helping a nonaligned country against a communist power, was marred by British policy of goading India to resolve Kashmir conflict with Pakistan. At the hour of crisis when India desperately needed immediate help, British behavior of putting conditions, made New Delhi deeply resentful.

In Britain and the US, the Macmillan and Kennedy governments approached the outbreak of India-China hostilities as an opportunity to bring India closer to western front from its tilt towards communism. Britain and America publicly condemned Chinese act of aggression. Macmillan sent a letter to Nehru in which he offered British endorsement to India's stand in the war with China. The USSR refused to meddle in a war between a communist 'brother' and a nonaligned friend. Later on, Khrushchev leaned towards China and in the United Nations the USSR called for India to enter into talks with China. Britain heeded to Nehru's request and provided automatic rifles to India. Britain clearly hoped that India would shed its garb of neutrality and see the benefits of joining western camp. Interestingly, the US thought that it was inappropriate and counterproductive to exploit India at its darkest hour. Pakistan vehemently opposed western aid to India. Its National Assembly unanimously condemned vast military aid to India and there was even a call for Pakistan's

² Ibid p-57

³ In hindsight, it becomes clear that USSR favored India in comparison to a Pakistan which was closely aligned to Anglo-American group.

⁴ Mishra, Anand Shankar. "British Policy Towards India-Pakistan Relations In The Perspective Of Military Alliances In Asia, 1953-1956." *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, vol. 39, no. 4, 1978, pp. 599-619. JSTOR, www.jstor.org/stable/41854878, p-601

withdrawal from SEATO and CENTO. India showed its appreciation to western stand by voting for an Anglo-American resolution at United Nations on nuclear testing.

India's reaction was as expected. India took British meddling as an infringement upon its sovereign right to conduct its foreign affairs. An Indian minister retorted in anger that even a defeat by the Chinese was preferable to India making concessions to Pakistan.⁵ McGarr writes, "During one interview with Nehru, the highly emotional Indian premier slammed his fist against a table and insisted to British minister Duncan Sandys that defeat by China must not be followed by a surrender to Pakistani blackmail."⁶

1965 India-Pakistan War and British Policy

War of 1965 between India and Pakistan was fought in two stages. In March-April, Pakistan attacked Rann of Kutch, which is a large area of salt marshes located mostly in the Indian state of Gujarat and the southern tip of Sind, Pakistan.⁷ There was an agreement between the two countries to hand over this matter to an international tribunal. Britain played an important role in it and Indian Prime Minister praised his British counterpart's very helpful role in the final stages of Rann negotiations. But British earned substantial brickbats in the second half of the war. In August 1965, Pakistan launched Operation Gibraltar and sent its regular forces in the guise of tribal militias in the hope of provoking insurgency in Jammu and Kashmir. To utmost surprise to all involved parties, India expanded the theater of war and attacked West Pakistan from the side of Punjab. Indian forces made gains at astonishing speed and reached the outskirts of city of Lahore. This time, it was the USSR, which played an important role in enacting a compromise between two warring nations. Indian Prime Minister and Pakistani President met in the city of Tashkent and a compromise ended the hostilities. China fully supported Pakistan in this war. It issued a stern warning to India and condemned its aggression.

Interestingly, while the United States maintained a more or less neutral stand, British Prime Minister, Harold Wilson, condemned India for its aggressive policies, when Indian forces marched towards Lahore. Even when Pakistan attacked Rann of Kutch, an American consular official noted that their British colleagues were disposed towards putting blame on the Indians. British reasoned that Pakistan patrols had been active in the Rann all along but the Indians were just waking up to fact and reacting.⁸ This position was in a divergence with American position, which mostly blamed Pakistan for hostilities, and pressured Ayub Khan not to use US supplied arms against India. Lord Mountbatten, Britain's Chief of Defense Staff, having conversed with Indian officials, noted that there was a particular disquiet that British had not come out more strongly to support the Indian's cast iron case in this dispute. Mountbatten was dismayed to discover that due to poor state of Anglo-Indian relations, plans to offer him the Colonelcy of a regular Indian Army regiment have been abandoned.

When Alexi Kosygin was able to convince Shastri and Ayub to come for a meeting in Tashkent and was able to cajole them into a compromise, an unnerved British Foreign Office acknowledged that for the Russians, the Tashkent meeting is a considerable triumph.... It may well give them a new and better entrée into the affairs of the sub-continent. Wilson's own cabinet felt that the Tashkent declaration represented a watershed in Britain's relationship with Indian subcontinent. George Brown, deputy leader of the Labor Party and First Secretary of State said that in exposing the weakness of the Commonwealth, Tashkent helped to convince Wilson that Britain's future was in Europe, rather than Africa or Asia.⁹

⁵ Ibid, p-174.

⁶ P-176.

⁷ Rann of Kutch, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rann_of_Kutch

⁸ McGarr, Paul M. "The Cold War in South Asia: Britain, the United States and the Indian Subcontinent, 1945-1965. Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, 2013, p-304.

⁹ Ibid, p-341

On the other hand, Washington saw little wrong in Soviet success in brokering a peace accord between India and Pakistan since both superpowers shared the objectives of building a strong and stable India and limiting Sino-Pakistani ties. After Shastri's death Nehru's daughter Indira Gandhi became the Prime Minister and during her tenure British influence waned even further and India came to regard the USSR as a true friend in all weathers.

1971 India-Pakistan War and British Policy

In all wars, which India-Pakistan fought, 1971 war was the most crucial one since it ended up changing the geography of the region—Pakistan was vivisected and its East wing emerged as an independent country of Bangladesh. Nixon-Kissinger team in the US famously tilted towards Pakistan and even sent its nuclear-armed warship in the Bay of Bengal. The US was clearly showing its gratitude to Pakistan for working as a mediator between Washington and Beijing. Mrs. Gandhi, the Indian Prime Minister, entered into a treaty of peace and friendship with the USSR, which basically meant if Washington would intervene in a would be Indo-Pak war than so would the USSR. It neutralized the American threat and India was able to win the war rather easily and as a consequence Bangladesh became an independent nation.

Debnath writes that indeed it would seem that a large portion of Britain's decisions were taken mostly spontaneously or ad hoc basis in response to circumstances as they arose. A semi-reactive approach to events as they arise rather than an overarching policy, was symptomatic of Edward Heath's government. For Guy Millard, the then head of Foreign Office, the 1971 crisis constituted a central dilemma for Britain. "One of our trouble is that we lack what one might call a philosophy of foreign policy. To a large extent we go on answering telegrams without having any clear idea of where exactly we want to get."¹⁰

Britain's immediate reaction to military crackdown in East Pakistan was to claim complete neutrality, which was perceived as support to Pakistan by India. British Foreign Secretary Alec-Douglas Homes informed House of Commons on March 29, 1971, "Everyone abhors violence. The President of Pakistan was faced with a situation in which his country might have been divided in half. We must allow the Pakistan authorities to deal with the matter without our intervention."¹¹ Two weeks into crisis, Edward Heath wrote a letter to Pakistani President that he remained a friend and a friend of Pakistan and fully cognizant of the fact that it was an internal matter of Pakistan.

British ability to ignore reports of genocide against Bengalis emanating from East Pakistan was remarkable. British Foreign Office advised Secretary of State that if he was pressed in parliament about genocide in East Pakistan, he should respond, "We can not, from direct evidence available to me, confirm allegations of army brutality against Hindus in East Pakistan."¹² Britain exclusively focused on technicalities of Genocide Conventions to absolve itself of any responsibility regarding atrocities taking place in East Pakistan. Debnath writes that the foreign office's restrictive interpretation of international humanitarian law supported the Heath government's basic unwillingness to acknowledge crimes committed by Pakistani state. The government's refusal to do so was largely based on an attempt to legitimize their commitment to non-interference, fuelled by concerns for national interests, a general sense of impotency, and fear of adverse consequences; yet it was also linked to the perception of the crisis as a civil war or armed struggle on 'both sides'.¹³

Conclusion: Tracing Causality

It is not very difficult to understand why Britain behaved the way it did. Why was Britain not able to formulate a concrete role in South Asia, in spite of being offered to take a lead in the region by the US? Why it mostly favored Pakistan over India? Why there was such lack of clarity and sense of

¹⁰ Debnath L. Angela, "Britain at the Birth of Bangladesh." Thesis submitted for the Doctor of Philosophy, University College, London, 2012, p-225.
https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/1546181/7/Debnath_Angela_PhD%20Thesis%20-%20Angela%20Debnath-1_redacted.pdf

¹¹ Ibid, p-71

¹² Ibid, p-100

¹³ Ibid, p-104.

purpose? Why there was no sense of clarity about what British interests were in South Asia? Why British policy was marked by general confusion and lack of cohesion? To answer these questions, one needs to understand the Britain after the end of Second World War was only the ghost image of its earlier self. During the decades of 1950s and 1960s, it had lost almost all of its erstwhile colonies. It suffered from severe economic instability after the Second World War. Its ability to provide economic and military aid was deeply compromised. The transition from a super power to just a middle level power was so sudden that it is hardly surprising that British political establishment was taken over by the sheer speed of events. For example, Britain badly wanted to keep Commonwealth intact. Again, in hindsight, it is clear that this intangible interest brought no real advantage to Britain apart from psychological benefits. This shows, the lack of clarity about national interests was due to misplaced priorities. The world, which Britain found after 1945 was dominated by the exigencies of the cold war. In this cold war, Britain found itself as a junior partner to the US. It was ill equipped to handle a lead in South Asia offered by the US. Later on, like during war in 1971, Britain just bowed down to decisions taken by the US. The burgeoning influence of the USSR generated a genuine fear psychosis in Britain. British foreign policy was in a general state of confusion. Given these factors, in hindsight, it is clear that confusion and lack of cohesion that marked British policy in South Asia, was only to be expected. Britain had not reconciled to its role of middle power, thus opportunity to play an important role in South Asia, proved to be futile. Being a cold war ally of the US, tilt towards Pakistan was natural. But sporadic desires for an independent foreign policy resulted in favoring India also on rare occasions. Instead of having a well thought out strategy, British foreign policy was confined to reacting to various events and even then British policy fluctuated and changed during the course of events. Britain realized, very painfully, that if it was to have any influence, it should concentrate on Europe and not on its erstwhile colonies of Asia and Africa.